

Supporting Material: Analyzing the future potential of defossilizing industrial specialty glass production with hydrogen by LCA

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Abstract

The glass industry is part of the energy-intensive industry, with most of the energy needed to melt the raw materials. To produce glass, temperatures between 1000 and 1600 °C are necessary. Presently, mostly fossil natural gas is the dominant energy source; oil is used less frequently. A direct electrification is not always possible. In this paper a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for specialty glass production is conducted, where the conventional fossil-based reference process uses heat produced in a furnace burning natural gas with oxygen. As an alternative hydrogen can be used in the furnace. This hydrogen can be produced on-site in an electrolyzer, using not only the hydrogen for the combustion but also the produced oxygen. Hydrogen can be produced alternatively off-site in a large scale electrolyzer to facilitate economy of scale. For the transport and distribution of this hydrogen different options are available. A rather new option are liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC), which bind the hydrogen in a chemical substance. However, temperatures around 300 °C are necessary to separate the hydrogen from the LOHC after transport. At the glass melt waste heat is available at the required temperature level to facilitate the dehydrogenation. The comparison is completed by the production of off-site hydrogen transported to the glass melt by conventional high-pressure trailer.

In this assessment, to power the electrolyzers the national grid mix of Germany is used. A time frame from 2020 till 2050 and its changing energy system towards defossilisation is analyzed. Regarding climate change, on-site hydrogen production causes the least impact for specialty glass production in 2050. However, negative trade-offs for other environmental impact categories, e.g. Metal depletion, are recorded.

Keywords

Life Cycle Assessment; Hydrogen supply; Glass production; Liquid organic hydrogen carrier

I LCI and technical data of the case studies

Table 1. Parameters of the PEM electrolysis of 1 MW (Barei et al., 2019; Raab, 2021)

	2020/2030	2050	Unit
Lifetime	20	20	a
Lifetime stack	7	10	a
Electricity demand	55.6	47.8	kWh/kg H ₂
Water demand	9	9	kg H ₂ O/kg H ₂

Table 2. Construction materials for the PEM electrolysis of 1 MW (Barei et al., 2019)

	2020/2030	2050	Unit
Stack			
Titanium	528	37	kg
Aluminum	27	54	kg
Stainless steel	100	40	kg
Copper	4.5	9	kg
Nafion®	16	2	kg
Activated carbon	9	4.5	kg
Iridium	750	37	g
Platinum	75	10	g
Balance of plant			
Low alloyed steel	4.8		t
High alloyed steel	1.9		t
Aluminum	< 100		kg
Copper	< 100		kg
Plastic	300		kg
Electronic material (power, control)	1.1		t
Process material (ad- sorbent, lubricant)	200		kg
Concrete	5.6		t

Table 3. Parameters of LOHC hydrogenation (Bauer et al., 2021)

Capacity	12	t/d
Temperature	250	°C
Lifetime catalyst	4	a
Electricity demand	0.5	kWh/kg H ₂

Table 4 Liquefaction parameters (Stolzenburg and Mubbala, 2013; Reu et al., 2017; Peschel, 2020)

Electricity demand		
2020	10.3	kWhel/kg H ₂
2030	8.53	kWhel/kg H ₂
2050	6.76	kWhel/kg H ₂
Hydrogen loss	1.65	%

Table 5 Transport parameters (Reuß et al., 2017)

	Liquid H ₂	LOHC	
Payload truck			
2020	3500	1530	kg H ₂
2030	3900	1530	kg H ₂
2050	4300	1530	kg H ₂
Diesel demand truck	32	32	l/100km

Table 6 Parameters dehydrogenation (Bauer et al., 2021)

Temperature	300	°C
Pressure	1.5-2.0	bar
Completeness of dehydration reaction	85	%
Lifetime catalyst	4	a
Electricity demand	0.18	kWh/kg H ₂
Heat demand	11.6	kWh/kg H ₂
Dibenzyl toluene loss	0.1	%/ cycle

II Flow diagrams of the case studies

The assessment includes five different technology options:

1. Fossil reference case: Natural gas,
2. Hydrogen transported by LOHC technology (H₂ LOHC),
3. Hydrogen transported by pipeline (H₂ Pipeline),
4. Hydrogen transported in a liquid form (H₂ liquid),
5. Hydrogen produced on-site (H₂ on-site).

Flow diagrams for options 1 and 2 can be found in the main article.

Figure 1 Flow diagram for hydrogen-based glass trough with transport of compressed hydrogen (CGH_2) in pipelines, option 3

Figure 2 Flow diagram for hydrogen-based glass trough with transport of liquid hydrogen (LH_2) in trucks, option 4

Electricity	11	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.3	3	1.5	0.3
Heat by Natural gas	1,440	0.30	0.32	1.04	0.87	0.9	578	2.0	0.4
O ₂ Production	27	0.07	0.04	0.07	0.17	37.1	6	3.5	0.7
Sum	1,478	0.40	0.38	1.14	1.11	38.3	587	7.0	1.4
LOHC									
H ₂ Transport	147	0.30	0.17	0.45	0.71	2.4	45	15.2	2.5
H ₂ Production	350	0.89	0.55	0.94	2.19	10.9	81	46.7	8.2
Electricity	11	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.3	3	1.5	0.3
Heat by Natural gas	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
O ₂ Production	22	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.14	30.9	5	2.9	0.6
Sum	530	1.28	0.76	1.48	3.11	44.5	135	66.3	11.4
H₂ Pipeline									
H ₂ Transport	77	0.17	0.04	0.33	0.35	1.5	26	8.8	1.9
H ₂ Production	350	0.89	0.55	0.94	2.19	10.9	81	46.7	8.2
Electricity	11	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.3	3	1.5	0.3
Heat by Natural gas	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂ Production	22	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.14	30.9	5	2.9	0.6
Sum	460	1.15	0.63	1.37	2.75	43.6	115	59.9	10.9
H₂ liquid									
H ₂ Transport	88	0.21	0.11	0.26	0.49	4.2	23	10.0	1.8
H ₂ Production	350	0.90	0.55	0.94	2.19	10.9	81	46.7	8.2
Electricity	11	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.3	3	1.5	0.3
Heat by Natural gas	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂ Production	22	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.14	30.9	5	2.9	0.6
Sum	471	1.18	0.71	1.29	2.89	46.3	113	61.1	10.8
H₂ on-site									
H ₂ Transport	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H ₂ Production	350	0.90	0.55	0.94	2.19	10.9	81	46.7	8.2
Electricity	11	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.3	3	1.5	0.3
Heat by Natural gas	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
O ₂ Production	3	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	3.8	1	0.4	0.1
Sum	364	0.93	0.57	0.98	2.28	15.0	85	48.5	8.5

Table 9 Selected normalized LCA results according to ReCiPe 2016, results in person equivalents per 1875 kg specialty glass production

	Climate change	Particulate matter	Ozone depletion	POF	Acidification	Water consumption	Fossil depletion	Land use	Metal depletion	Sum
Natural gas	0.19	0.02	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.14	0.60	0.00	0.00	1.03
H₂ on-site	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.09	0.01	0.00	0.34

IV References

- Barei, K., de la Rua, C., Mockl, M., and Hamacher, T. (2019). Life cycle assessment of hydrogen from proton exchange membrane water electrolysis in future energy systems. *Applied Energy* 237, 862-872. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.01.001>.
- Bauer, F., Cadavid, A., Gawlick, J., Frohlich, T., Hildebrand, J., Patyk, A., et al. (2021). *Technischer Anhang (Engl.: Technical Appendix)*. Frankfurt: DECHEMA.
- Peschel, A. (2020). Industrial Perspective on Hydrogen Purification, Compression, Storage, and Distribution. *Fuel Cells* 20(4), 385-393. doi: 10.1002/face.201900235.
- Raab, M. (2021). "Analysen zu der Kopernikus P2X Wertschopfungskette zur Herstellung von Wasserstoff uber die PEM-Elektrolyse: Techno-okonomische Analyse (Engl: Analyses of the Copernicus P2X value chain for the production of hydrogen via PEM electrolysis: techno-economic analysis.)," in *3. Roadmap des Kopernikus-Projektes „Power-to-X“*, eds. F. Ausfelder & H. Dura. (Frankfurt: DECHEMA), 92-94.
- Reu, M., Grube, T., Robinius, M., Wasserscheid, P., and Stolten, D. (2017). Seasonal storage and alternative carriers: A flexible hydrogen supply chain model. *Applied Energy* 200(-), 290–302.
- Stolzenburg, K., and Mubbala, R. (2013). "Hydrogen Liquefaction Report - Whole Chain Assessment," in *Integrated Design for Demonstration of Efficient Liquefaction of Hydrogen (IDEALHY)*. (Brussels: Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH JU)).